

OPEN**An Empirical Study to Measure Effectiveness of Training Program Between Existing and Potential Women Entrepreneurs**Sania Sami¹ and S. Roychowdhury²

Entrepreneurship has been acknowledged as a crucial driver for the development and growth of the economy as it led to the generation of employment, produces goods and services, increases gross national product (GDP), and finally resulted in increasing gross national income. Fostering and promoting entrepreneurship is not circumscribe to giving a boost to incumbent entrepreneurs but it also engirdled in ingraining the entrepreneurial essence among the juvenile owing to the fact, today's adolescents are tomorrow's well-heeled entrepreneurs. Thus, this research is undertaken to provide an empirical and theoretical understanding to measures the extent of effectiveness training have across both established as well as potential women entrepreneurs. The study includes women across West Bengal, Kolkata. This entrepreneurship training and skill development program was conducted to promote and foster entrepreneurship among homepreneurs and potential women entrepreneurs. The training and skill program includes tracks viz., the essence of entrepreneurship, challenges in entrepreneurship, development of communication, networking, marketing and business problemsolving skills, legal formalities, and efforts were also made to promote sustainable entrepreneurship among the trainees. The training and skill development program provides financial assistance to few innovative homepreneurs and potential entrepreneurs to promote and as well as to start-up of business. The effectiveness of the program was evaluated using Kirkpatrick's 4-Level Training Evaluation Model. From the study, it was inferred that the training program was effective both in promoting and fostering entrepreneurship between both established as well as potential women entrepreneurs.

Keywords: potential women entrepreneurs, McNemar test, skill development, training, women entrepreneurs

Introduction

Across the globe, entrepreneurship has been acknowledged and recognizes as the crucial solution to unemployment or underemployment, poverty, increase of gross domestic product and per capita income, and further, it paves the way to economic growth. Many governments as well as non- governments institutions have come forward with training intervention to promote and uplift women status through women entrepreneurship. Martin et al., (2013) in his research

have asserted that entrepreneurship training led to increase in business start-ups. According to the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor, there is not much studies on entrepreneurship training and measuring the effectiveness of training or how training assists in overcoming the business challenges (Martinez et al., 2010). Lack of education and training are the major constraints to success of women entrepreneurship. Thus, training becomes essential to foster

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.entrepreneurship between potential and existing women entrepreneurs.

With time and tide, India has also necessitated the development and fostering of entrepreneurship across states for the growth of the economy. The study undertaken with primary objective to measure the effectiveness of the training program across both potential and existing entrepreneurs in Kolkata

The following hypothesis was formulated concerning the research objectives:

Null hypothesis (H₁): The training program was not effective.

The research paper has been organized in the following way: the next section includes literature review on training and entrepreneurship that assists in identifying the research gap. Next section is methodology for data analysis and it has been followed by results of data analysis that have also been discussed. Finally, the paper ends with conclusion.

Literature

This section includes a broad domain of literature review is to provide constructive understanding about entrepreneurship, women entrepreneurship, and the need for training to promote entrepreneurship spirit among potential and established entrepreneurs.

Entrepreneurship

Over the last two decades, there have been extensive studies and research has been done in the context of women entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurship may be defined as the technique of both innovation and as well as exploiting the opportunities through efforts and perseverance along with undertaking financial, psychological, and social risks related to business to earn profit, self-satisfaction, and independence.

(Hisrich & Drnovsek, 2002). Researchers have recognized entrepreneurship as a crucial driver to economic, social, cultural, and environmental development. Entrepreneurship success is also acknowledged as a crucial phenomenon, that is ascertained by several factors viz., economic, demographic, personality, innovation, financial assistance, and training factor. Of all the factors training is the crucial factor for promoting entrepreneurship among potential and established women entrepreneurs.

Women Entrepreneurs

Cantillon was the first person to put forward the initial definition of the word entrepreneur in 1755. He believed an entrepreneur is an adventurer who purchases goods at a certain price with a motive to sell the same in the future at an uncertain price (Cantillon, 2010). Harper (1996) defined entrepreneurs as profit-seekers who identified business problems and uncertainties and attempt to resolve the same. He further broadened entrepreneur activities that involves innovation also. Thus, the entrepreneur is responsible for undertakes risks and decisions that determined the environment through their activities.

According to the government of India (2012), women will be considered an entrepreneur if they have the majority of financial share (51%) of the capital and they provide minimum 51% of business employment to women.

From the sixth economic census (2014) it was found that only 14% of women in India run or own businesses. There is a multitude of reasoning to promote entrepreneurship through providing proper and structured training programs.

Women Entrepreneurship Training and Skill Development Program (WET&SDP)

Past studies have revealed that there was a significant growth in women start-up owing to continuous business evolution, new technologies, and innovation that also led to economic transformation (Gibb,

2002, Schneider, 2017). There is a continuous necessitate of training about women entrepreneurs to improves their understanding, overcome business challenges, develop business skills, and motivates them to undertakes the right decisions and risks at right time.

Training Model

A training program was conducted to serve the four crucial elements viz., entrepreneurial skill, business skill, mentoring, and provide financial assistance. A new model was developed that provides a framework of women entrepreneurship

training and skill development program (WETSDP) a sincere and enthusiastic attempt has been made to promote and foster entrepreneurship among women of West Bengal. Training program must contemplate intense interactive sessions to ensure high learning. The training program involves a wide range of training techniques viz., factory visit, case study/ life experience, activity session, discussing entrepreneurs project, idea pitching, and lecture method. Most training techniques are highly engaging and interactive including the lecture method (traditional method) where transfer of knowledge is generally one way. Thus, teaching aids like projectors and PowerPoint presentations were modestly employed to ensure interactive sessions. Table 1. exhibit the training techniques, extent of interaction and learning involvement which is identified through extant literature.

Table 1: Training Techniques, Extent of Interaction and Learning Involvement

Training Technique	Extent of Interaction	Learning Involvement
Factory visit	Intense	High
Case Study/ life experience	Medium	Modest
Activity session	Intense	High
Entrepreneur project	Intense	High
Idea pitching	Intense	High
Lecture (PPT)	Medium	Modest

Effectiveness of Training Model: Kirkpatrick Model

Kirpatrick's (1967) model was used to measure the effectiveness of WET&SDP was measured at four levels of criteria using viz., reaction measures, learning measure, behavior measures and results in measure.

Reaction Measure: The first criterion is "response," which determines if trainers find the training entertaining, beneficial, and relevant to their work.

Learning Measure: gauges the learning of each trainer to measure if they acquire the intended knowledge, skills, and attitude to the training.

Behavior Measure: Behavior measures one of the most crucial steps in the Kirkpatrick Model, whether

trainers were impacted by the training and if they're applying their learning to achieve their business goals.

Results Measure: The result measure, is related to direct results. It measures the learning against the business outcomes, growth, profitability, etc.

Using the Kirkpatrick Model initiate an actionable measurement plan that clearly define goals, measure results and assists in identifying the target areas and training impact. Further, analyzing data at each level assists organizations to evaluate the effectiveness of the training results.

Research Gap

From the extant literature review it was ascertained that there have been many researches have evaluated the effectiveness of training between the employees in the organisations but there has been almost no study that measure the effectiveness of entrepreneurship training program across potential and established women entrepreneurs. Thus, this research will assist if such training program can assist in uplifting women status in the society by fostering the spirit of entrepreneurship between both potential and existing entrepreneurs.

Research Methodology

Quasi-experimental study has been applied as research methodology. The WET&SDP was conducted in the local area of Kolkata, West Bengal. Structured questionnaire was used as instrumental tool to collect the data from 45 women trainees of them 25 women entrepreneurs and 20 potential entrepreneurs located in Kolkata.

The SPSS software v. 26 was used for the statistical analysis. The study employed non-parametric test

McNemar to measure the effectiveness of the training program.

Data Analysis: Result and Discussion

This section contains results that offer data and explain the research's primary conclusions. The interpretation of the results is part of the debate, which adds to the research's overall relevance.

Demographic Profile of the women trainees

Most of the potential and existing women entrepreneur trainees were age between 23-28 and 36-43.

The majority of the women trainee across both the group were graduate. Majority of the respondents were married. Further, existing women entrepreneurs were mostly running sole proprietorship and majority have registered their businesses. Trainees were included from all the three sectors viz., manufacturing, trading, and service sectors.

McNemar Test: A test for significance of changes in pre and post potential and established trainee group

The McNemar test was used to assess the effectiveness of WET&SDP on potential (21 women) and existing (24) women entrepreneurs. Both future and current learners were given training so that they could either start up or expand the firm. The McNemar test was used on both potential (21 women) and existing (21 women) entrepreneurs to see if the training measures the impact of WET&SDP on women entrepreneurs (24 women). Both groups were given training so that they could either start up or expand the firm. To see if the training programme was successful and if a similar programme could be implemented on a wider group of women across the state to encourage women's entrepreneurship. "Are you certain that you will establish a business following the programme?" the trainees were asked to answer "Yes" or "No."

"Are you positive that your firm will increase after training?" was questioned of current learners. According to the findings, 14 women said yes before training and 6 said no after training, whereas 20

women said yes after training and one said no. Six trainees modify their responses from no to yes, but just one trainee's reaction remains intact, according to the McNemar test. Because the p -value is lower than 0.05 the null hypothesis will be rejected and it was inferred that the training programme was effective.

Conclusion

The entrepreneurial training is imparted to promote the spirit of entrepreneurship between women in Kolkata. From the research it was found that training program was effective in increasing the skill and knowledge of the potential and existing entrepreneurs. The training program not only assists in gaining new insight into business knowledge but also aware women about various opportunities and challenges which women may encounter and overcome through applying those skills and knowledge acquired by them during training. The study also concluded that similar training program must be conducted to larger number of women for upliftment of the women status in the society.

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